

Science

A UNIQUE HERBAL COMBINATION WITH AGNIKARMA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF VATKANTAKA- A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Vatkantak is one type of vat-vyadhi, which is most common form of articular disorder. Today's era, continue standing work like conductor, heavy weight, labour work, travelling and injury etc leads to this disease. All the osteoarthritis diseases in Ayurveda have been described under the heading of 'vatvyadhi' vatkantak can be correlated with the calcaneal spur. Here in the case study a female patient of age 45 years presenting with clinical features of vatkantaka and was treated with Agnikarma got relief within 15 days.

Keywords: Vatkantaka; Agnikarma; Ayurvedic Management; Effective Therapy.

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1. Introduction

VataKantak⁽¹⁾ is one of the *Vata Vyadhi*⁽²⁾ which occurs in *Gulpha sandhi*⁽³⁾ region. It is characterized by *shool* (pain) and *shoth* (Inflammation) in *khudak* (Heel). It can be co-related with calcaneal spur in modern science. Calcaneal spur⁽⁴⁾ is a condition in which Osteophytes (bone spur) are formed on calcareous bone⁽⁵⁾ and is characterized by pain during walking, swelling and tenderness over heel.

According to acharya Sushruta, Agnikarma is the superior in all Para surgical procedure. For eradication of various diseased conditions of *Sira*, *Snayu* and *Sandhi* in which pain is a predominant symptom.

2. Aim and Objective

- 1) Conceptual and clinical study of *Vatakantak* and Calcaneal spur
- 2) To assess the clinical the efficacy of *Agnikarma* in the management of *Vatakantaka*

3. Case Report

History of Personal Illness

A female patient aged 45 years presented with the complaint of *gulf sandhi shool*(ankle joint pain) and *gulf sandhi shoth* (Inflammation at ankle joint),*chakraman kashtata* (difficulty in walking) these symptoms from 1 month But from 15 days patient increase the severity of symptoms.

The present case study is successful Ayurvedic management of a case of *vatkantak* (Calcaneal spur). A 45 year old female patient came to us with chief compliant of –

Table 1: Showing symptoms & duration of patient

Sr.No	Chief Complaints	Duration
1	<i>gulf sandhi shool</i> (ankle joint pain)	15 days
2	<i>gulf sandhi shoth</i> (Inflammation at ankle joint)	15 days
3	<i>Chakraman-kashatata</i> (difficulty in walking)	1 month

4. Astavidha Pariksha

Nadi (pulse) = 78/min.

Mala (stool) = *awastambha*

Mutra (urine) = 3-4 times in a day

Jeeva (tounge) = *Eshat saam*.

Agni = *prakrut*

Shabda (speech) = *prakrut*

Akruti = *Madhyama*.

Bala = *Madhyama*.

Raktadaaba (B.P) = 120/70 mm/Hg.

vatkantak (calcaneun spur)

Agnikarma shalaka

5. Materials and Methods

Center of study: S. S. N.J. Ayurvedic Hospital, Solapur, India.

Method of sampling& study design: Simple randomized single case study.

Materials

Table 2: Showing material used in study

Sr.No	Dravya	Dose	Duration	Anupan
1	Yograj guggulu	200 mg	1 pack Twice in day	Luke warm water
2	samirpannaga	125 mg		
3	Dashmula	500 mg		
4	Guduchi	1 gm		
5	Gandhrava haritaki	1 gm	At night	Luke warm water

Table 2: Panchakarma

Sr. No.	Procedure	Site
1	Agnikarma	at ankle joint

Photo which show agnikarma points

agnikarma given on pad pradeshi

Hetu seven

Ahar- *ruksha,shit(cold)*, bread, behari products oily,non veg dite *katu tikta kashaya rasatamak* diet.

Vihar- heavy weight and continue standing house work.

Samprati**Samprati-Ghatak:**

- *Dosha– vata dosha prakop*
- *Dushya – asthi*
- *Srotas – asthivaha*
- *Srotodusti – sanchaya vrutti*
- *Udhbhavasthana – asthi,sandhi*
- *Vyaktasthana – gulf pradeshi*

Samprapti Bhanga

Action of all individual drug mentioned in following table-

Sr. No	Dravya	Action
1	<i>Yograj gugulu^{6,7}</i>	<i>vatshamak, vatashoolnashak, strotobandanashak</i>
2	<i>Samirpannag⁸</i>	<i>vata kaphaghana</i>
3	<i>Guduchi⁹</i>	<i>Rasayani, vayasta, jwaragni, vatkaphagn</i>
4	<i>Dashashmool</i>	<i>vatanashak,</i>
5	<i>Gandrav haritaki</i>	<i>anulomak, vatashulanashak</i>

6. Observation and Result

The results observed after the treatment: Improvement in signs and symptoms of the patient. Relief was found in dragging pain, numbness and tingling sensation. Gait has improved.

Walking Distance

Before treatment: - Patient had severe pain after walking 100 mts.

After treatment: - Patient could easily walk without pain about 200 mts.

Walking Time

Before treatment: - Patient took around ten minutes to walk 100 steps.

After treatment: patient took around five minutes to walk 100 steps.

No significant change was observed in x ray

Above results after *Agnikarma* treatment only.

7. Discussion and Conclusion

Agnikarma therapy shows highly significant results in all signs and symptoms, especially in case of pain as it is one of the most uncomfortable factors for patient. The entire treatment was tolerated comfortably by the patients. There were no side effects noticed in any of the patients. The procedure was simple economical and can be done in OPD level gives instant relief to most of the patients, but still to avoid the reoccurrence of the disease and to break the *Samprapti* the patient may need to continue on oral shaman medication. The Pain relief provided by *Agnikarma* presents a window of opportunity in the clinical management of calcaneal spur.

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